

S-2 GLASS® FIBER:

ITS ROLE IN MILITARY APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Owens-Corning Fiberglas Corporation's S-2 Glass® fiber is a high performance/low cost reinforcement with properties superior to conventional E-glass and a cost between E-glass and other high performance fibers, such as carbon and aramid.

First developed in the period from 1966-1968, S-2 Glass products have continued to evolve and a significant data base has been generated. Available in products that meet most every processing need, S-2 Glass reinforcements are currently being used in a large number of aircraft, automotive, industrial, consumer and military applications.

This paper will cover a brief introduction of S-2 Glass fiber products, typical fiber and composite properties and product benefits. Applications now using S-2 Glass fibers will be presented. The paper will stress the use of S-2 Glass fibers used in military applications with emphasis on new developments in the use of light weight composites using S-2 in military vehicle structures and light weight armor.

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Introduction

In the late 1960's, Owens-Corning Fiberglas Corporation identified a need for a fiber with better performance than conventional E glass and lower cost than high strength S-Glass® reinforcement. S-Glass reinforcements, developed during the early 1960's, found extensive use in strategic missiles. The high cost of the special sizing systems and stringent quality control and testing required for that application, however, made S-Glass fiber unsuitable for broader use in the emerging "composites revolution". In response, Owens-Corning researchers sought to develop a high performance reinforcement to fill the void in the materials spectrum between E glass and such fibers as carbon and aramid. The result was S-2 Glass fiber, a reinforcement with physical properties appreciably greater than E glass at a price per pound significantly less than carbon and aramid fiber.

Today S-2 Glass reinforcements, available in products that meet most every advanced composite processing need, are being specified as a high performance reinforcement in a wide variety of applications. The product line consists of starch oil sized yarn and epoxy compatible yarn for weaving or braiding, and three roving products for prepregging, filament winding or pultrusion. A roving for sheet molding compound and chopped strands for reinforcing polymers, such as nylon and other thermoplastics, are also available on a development basis.

Owens-Corning Fiberglas Corporation's 463 epoxy compatible roving was developed in 1974 to attain improved shear values required for helicopter blades. In 1973, OCF 449 roving, also epoxy compatible, was developed to improve wet strength retention in moisture sensitive applications. Although there is no clear distinction between the products, each has been specified for key applications. Customers indicate that 449 wets out slightly better than 463 in amine cured resins while the two wet out equally well in anhydride cured resins. 449 and 463 have rapidly become the standard rovings for low cost/high performance filament wound and prepreg applications, such as helicopter blades, pressure vessels and aircraft flooring.

A third roving, P-365A is a general purpose reinforcement demonstrating excellent performance in filament winding, pultrusion and hand lay-up. Compatible with epoxy polyester and vinyl ester resin systems, it can be used in such applications as wind energy blades, pressure vessels, fishing rods and high performance boats.

OCF 449, 463 and P-365A are available in a yield range from 250 to 1,250 yards per pound. In addition, OCF 493 epoxy compatible yarn and 636 starch oil sized yarn are available in single end twisted form for weaving and multiple end wound form for braiding.

Commercially available S-2 Glass products are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I
Advanced Composites Products

<u>Number</u>	<u>Glass</u>	<u>Product Form</u>	<u>Available Yields</u>	<u>Resin Compat-ibility</u>	<u>Fabrication Process</u>	<u>Comments</u>
449	S-2	Roving	250, 750, 1250	Epoxy	Filament Winding Prepreg Pultrusion	Prefer over 463 unless customer has very sensitive process. Will not pull from inside
463	S-2	Roving Chopped Strands	250, 750, 1250 1/4"	Epoxy	Filament Winding Prepreg Pultrusion Compression Molding	Processes slightly better than 449
471	S-2	Roving	113, 250	Polyester	SMC Compression Molding	Designed primarily for structural applications
485	S-2	Chopped Strands Roving	1/8", 1/4" 250	Nylon	Thermoplastic Injection Molding Filament Winding	Sizing similar to 416 E Glass
493	S-2	Yarn	G150, G75	Epoxy	Weaving Braiding	Available in various twisted and plied combinations
636	S-2	Yarn	G150, G75	Not com- patible with resins	Weaving Braiding	Must be heat cleaned and post treated

All products meet Mil Spec R-60346C, Type I or IV

Properties

The most important advantage of S-2 Glass fiber over E glass is a 35-40 percent improvement in tensile strength. Other composite mechanical properties are also improved. Compared to E glass, S-2 Glass fiber has better flexural strength (20-40 percent), compressive strength (20-25 percent), density (2-4 percent lower), and Young's modulus (18-20 percent).

Glass Properties

The physical, mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of E glass and S-2 Glass fiber are compared in Table II. The physical and mechanical properties are measured on unsized fibers; thermal and electrical properties are based on bulk glass. A comparison of corrosion resistance is provided in Table III. As indicated, S-2 Glass is more resistant to strong acids. The information in Table III was generated using bare glass. Therefore, it characterizes the materials but does not necessarily describe how they will perform in a laminate, because resin has a major influence in determining the corrosion resistance of a composite material.

TABLE II
Comparative Data
S-2 Glass® and E-Glass

Properties of Glass Fibers	S-2 Glass®	E glass	
Physical Properties*			
Specific Gravity - Fibers gms/cc	2.49	2.60	
Density - lb./cu. in.	.090	.094	
Mechanical Properties*			
Virgin Tensile Strength 70°F, psi × 10 ³	665	500	
Modulus of Elasticity			
72°F, psi × 10 ⁶	12.6	10.5	
72°F, psi × 10 ⁶ (After heat compaction)	13.5	12.4	
1000°F, psi × 10 ⁶ (After heat compaction)	12.9	11.8	
Elongation at 72°F, %	5.4	4.8	
Thermal Properties**			
Coefficient of Expansion in./in./°F × 10 ⁶	1.3	2.8	
Specific Heat at 75°F	0.176	0.192	
Softening Point °F	1,778	1,155	
Strain Point °F	1,400	1,140	
Annealing Point °F	1,490	1,215	
Electrical Properties**			
Dielectric Constant at 72°F	1 MHz	5.34	6.33
	10 KHz	5.21	6.13
Power Factor at 72°F (Loss Tangent)	1 MHz	0.002	0.001
	10 KHz	0.0068	0.0039
Acoustical Properties*			
Velocity of Sound	Calculated ft./sec.	19,200	17,500
	Measured ft./sec.	—	18,000
Optical Properties**			
Index of Refraction	1.523	1.547	

*Properties were determined on glass fibers.

**Properties were determined on bulk glass.

TABLE III
Corrosion Resistance

	S-2 Glass® Fiber (% Wt. Loss)
10% H ₂ SO ₄	5.7
Conc. HCl	1.4
10% NH ₃	7.3
H ₂ O (distilled)	1
10% NaOH	66
10% KOH	66

Conditions: "G" Fiber Bare Glass
96°C (205°F)
One week immersion

Mechanical Properties

Comparisons of strand tensile strength, NOL ring, short beam shear strength and NOL hydroburst properties of epoxy laminates made with E glass roving, E glass Type-30™ roving and S-2 Glass roving are included in the reference tables and figures. As indicated, the strand tensile strength (Table IV) of S-2 Glass fiber is much higher than E glass; there is, however, no significant difference between E glass roving and E glass Type-30 roving. Whereas strand tensile is primarily reinforcement dependent, short beam shear strength (Tables V and VI) is primarily matrix and bond dependent. As a result, there is very little difference between the short beam shear strength of laminates made with E glass compared to S-2 Glass fiber.

TABLE IV
Impregnated Strand Tensile

Product	Tensile Strength (psi × 10 ³)
456, E	277.5
462, E	271.5
463, S-2 Glass Strand	519.9
Resin: DER 331 Amine Cure, MPDA	
Cure: 2 hours at 350° F.	
Test: ASTM 2343	

TABLE V
NOL Ring
Short Beam Shear Strength
Anhydride Cure

	456, E	462, E	463, S-2 Glass Fiber
Dry Strength (psi × 10 ³)	N.T.	10.2	9.7
6 hour boil (psi × 10 ³)		9.5	8.8
% Retention		93	91
Resin: DER 331 Anhydride Cure, Lindride 6			
Cure: 1.5 hours at 175°F. 2 hours at 350°F.			
Test: ASTM 2344			

TABLE VI
NOL Ring Short Beam
Shear Strength
Amine Cure

	456, E	462, E	463, S-2 Glass Fiber
Dry Strength (psi × 10 ³)	9.9	9.4	9.2
6 hour boil (psi × 10 ³)	9.7	8.9	9.1
% Retention	98	95	99
Resin: DER 331 Amine Cure, MPDA			
Cure: 2 hours @ 250° F 2 hours @ 350° F			
Test: ASTM 2344			

The composite breaking strength of E glass and S-2 Glass fiber in an epoxy matrix can be determined by comparing Figures 1 and 2. The stress state produced by the NOL ring hydroburst is one of pure tension (hoop stress) in the fiber (0°) direction. Thus the composite strength results reflect a fiber dominated property.

The breaking stress of S-2 Glass fiber is approximately 76 percent higher than that of E glass. After emersion in boiling water, a severe strength degradation test, the E glass laminate (462) retains 66 percent of its strength while the S-2 Glass laminate (463) retains 72 percent. Many industry leaders feel a six-hour water boil emersion test is representative of the exposure that the average application will see during its life cycle. Most glass fiber-reinforced laminates retain greater than 90 percent of their strength after six hours of exposure.

Fabric Laminates

Large quantities of E and S-2 Glass yarn, having a starch oil sizing system, are sold to weavers. The yarn is then woven into fabric, sized with proprietary treatments and sold to prepreg manufacturers. In turn, prepreg is sold for contact and autoclave molding in various markets. The mechanical properties of style 181, S-2 Glass fiber and E glass fabrics in epoxy resin are shown in Table VII. The results represent a composite average of values supplied by various weavers from fabric with different finishes. The S-2 Glass yarn increases flexural strength 38 percent, tensile strength 6 percent and flexural modulus 14 percent, compared to E glass. As indicated in Table VIII, laminates made with uni-directional S-2 Glass prepreg show 67 percent higher tensile, 6 percent higher flexural strength and 15 percent higher modulus than those made with E glass.

TABLE VII
Mechanical Properties of Style 181
S-2 Glass® and E-Glass
Fabrics-Epoxy Systems
(Avg. Properties of Various Weavers)

psi × 10 ³			
Property	S-2 Glass®	E glass	% Improvement
• Flexural Strength, Dry	113.5	82.4	38
Flexural Strength, Wet	111.9	74.6	
• Compressive Strength, Dry	65.7	62.0	6
Compressive Strength, Wet	61.6	56.7	
• Tensile Strength, Dry	81.6	57.2	43
Tensile Strength, Wet	82.2	55.9	
• Flexural Modulus, Dry	4.0	3.5	14
Flexural Modulus, Wet	4.1	3.4	
• % Resin	34.4	37.5	

The above properties represent a composite average of values using a variety of finishes, supplied by various weavers. These values are neither certified by Owens-Corning Fiberglas Corporation nor express any warranty as to their validity.

TABLE VIII
Unidirectional Prepreg Properties (S-2 Glass®)
Room Temperature
(EPOXY RESIN)

	A	B	C
0° Tensile Strength (KSI)	282	240	251
0° Tensile Modulus (MSI)	6.8	8.2	6.9
0° Flexural Strength (KSI)	196	195	181
0° Flexural Modulus (MSI)	8.1	8.5	6.5
Short Beam Shear (KSI)	11.8	8.7	12
Resin Content (%)	28	23	29

Data was supplied by three prepreg manufacturers using three different epoxy resin systems.

Hybrids

Although hybridization is not a new concept, the increasing use of high cost/high performance fibers, such as carbon and aramid, has made the need for minimizing cost while obtaining the desired properties more critical. In many cases, glass and other fibers can be combined to obtain the best features of each (strength, modulus, fatigue, impact, light weight) while minimizing cost.

The reinforcements can be blended in unidirectional or bidirectional woven fabric, prepregged tape, continuous fibers or chopped fibers. Hybrids can be processed by most standard methods, including hand lay-up/autoclave, filament winding, pultrusion, compression molding and injection molding. Various laminating methods, such as interply, intraply and selective placement can optimize desired properties at the lowest possible cost.

The major advantages of hybridization are reduced cost, balanced strength and stiffness, increased impact strength, improved fracture toughness, reduced machine sensitivity and galvanic corrosion resistance. The major advantages of S-2 Glass fiber compared to carbon fiber are tensile strength, impact strength and cost. The major disadvantages are density and modulus. Compared to aramid, S-2 Glass strengths are cost, heat resistance, processability and compressive strength; the weakness is strength-to-weight ratio.

S-2 Glass Fiber Applications

During the late 1960's and early 1970's, S-2 Glass fiber emerged in several advanced composite applications.

One was S-2 Glass fiber chopped strands for molding the M-16 A1 grenade launcher stock. Another early, successful application was filament wound oxygen bottles for NASA's Skylab project. Interestingly, these bottles were the largest pieces to be recovered in Australia after Skylab's fiery plunge back to earth in 1979.

Current successful S-2 Glass fiber applications include pressure vessels, aircraft components, and tactical and strategic weapons. In addition, industrial and consumer equipment applications of S-2 Glass fiber are growing.

Pressure Vessels

The combination of low cost, durability and structural integrity that S-2 Glass roving provides, compared to other materials, makes it ideal for pressure vessels. Typically wet filament wound with S-2 Glass fiber and epoxy resin, composite pressure vessels for breathing apparatuses have gained rapid acceptance by firemen, policemen, miners, mountain climbers and medical rescue personnel. S-2 Glass fiber, for example, recently played an important role in a Dutch expedition up the face of Mount Everest. The climbers' tanks, constructed by overwrapping seamless aluminum liners with high strength S-2 Glass roving, provided a 50 percent weight savings over conventional aluminum

cylinders. Down at sea level, firemen across the country are also breathing easier because of light weight composite units. Compared to steel, the composite tanks are smaller (5.25 inch diameter versus as much as 6.7 inch), weigh half as much (11 pounds versus 22) and contain the same amount of compressed air. The weight savings of composite vessels is even more important for miners whose lives depend on one-hour emergency breathing apparatuses worn around the waist all day long.

In addition, S-2 Glass fiber-wrapped vessels are being used increasingly for aircraft jet engine starter bottles and life raft inflation cylinders.

Aircraft

Panels made from nomex honeycomb core sandwiched between two S-2 Glass fiber-reinforced epoxy skins continue to revolutionize the aircraft flooring market. Measuring approximately 0.4 inch thick and weighing roughly 0.6 pounds per square foot, the panels are lighter and stronger than the aluminum/balsa panels they are replacing. In Boeing's new 767, S-2 Glass fiber-reinforced composite flooring achieved a 30 percent weight savings at reasonable cost. In addition, the unique qualities of unidirectional S-2 Glass fiber distribute stress throughout the panel, and life expectancy of the flooring is at least two and one-half times that of aluminum panels. Boeing (757, 767) and McDonnell-Douglas (DC10, DC980) are currently specifying floors made with S-2 Glass fiber, and many airlines are refitting older aircraft with composite panels to conserve fuel. S-2 Glass fiber use is also growing in other commercial aircraft applications. Interior parts, such as cargo liners and galley walls, are becoming increasingly prevalent because of the high strength, light weight and corrosion resistance of the material.

Fiberglass composite helicopter rotor blades have been under development for more than 25 years; and because of superior fatigue strength, repairability and resistance to ballistic damage, they are well on their way to becoming standard for U.S. military and commercial helicopters.

Successful military applications have quickly led to civilian use. Bell's 214B was the first commercial helicopter with composite blades certified by the FAA. The composite blades are also on the new 214ST, which is designed to operate with loads of 7,000 pounds at a speed of more than 150 knots and a range of more than 400 miles. In addition, Bell is specifying composite blades for its 412, the first time composites have been used on a four-blade rotor system.

The Boeing-Chinook is equipped with both composite blades and external fuel tanks for long distance servicing of off-shore oil rigs. Sikorsky and Bell are also increasing their composite use. Sikorsky's new S-76 has an S-2 Glass fiber-reinforced main rotor head and Bell's Textron 222 and 214ST were recently converted to include three key S-2 Glass fiber composite parts: a vibration-absorbing leaf spring, an engine cowling and a rotor blade hub.

The spring, made with unidirectional S-2 Glass fiber composites and rubber, substantially reduces cabin vibration and represents the

first time Bell design engineers selected composite materials not as a replacement for steel or a aluminum, but as a first choice.

Industrial and Consumer

S-2 Glass fiber is currently being used in a number of industrial/consumer applications worthy of more specific review.

In the automotive market, the high temperature resistance of S-2 Glass fiber makes it a good alternative to asbestos. Automotive engineers have found, for example, that after more than one million miles of vehicle testing, at temperatures up to 1,200°F, standard glass fiber garter gaskets equal asbestos in performance.

S-2 Glass products surpass that level by 200°F. A major automotive company has selected S-2 Glass fiber for garter gaskets for 80 percent of the company's U.S. passenger-car and light-truck catalytic converters. The garter gasket helps protect the monolith -- an extruded, ceramic honeycomb component in the converter -- from gas bypass, the leaking of uncleaned exhaust emissions.

One of the most recent automotive applications of S-2 Glass fiber is a flexible driveshaft. Utilizing a S-2 Glass fiber-reinforced urethane matrix, the driveshaft transmits torsional power and inherently accommodates shaft misalignment. The new product was awarded first prize in the developmental category of the Society of the Plastics Industry Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute 1984 Product Awards Program.

In consumer markets, S-2 Glass fiber is used in arrow shafts and fishing rods. In the former, S-2 Glass fibers are oriented in a design that allows the arrow to withstand punishing hunting environments. S-2 Glass fiber, because of excellent impact resistance, protects the shaft from crush, slap and other impact related problems. Fishing rods, too, require durability and resilience. S-2 Glass fiber is used because it is more durable than rods made of competing materials, such as boron and graphite.

One of the first recreational applications of glass fiber-reinforced plastic was in pole vaulting. In 1952, Bob Mathias, the two-time Olympic decathlon champion, revolutionized the sport with a fiberglass pole. Since then, increasingly sophisticated technology has favored S-2 Glass fiber to cut weight and provide greater flexibility. Poland's Wladyslaw Kozakiewicz, for example, soared to a gold medal in the 1980 Olympic Games with the help of an S-2 Glass fiber-reinforced pole. And the fiber was used again in the 1984 Los Angeles Olympics.

S-2 Glass fiber is going places fast these days in another demanding sports application. The fiber is being used extensively in unidirectional fabric that boat builders hand lay-up to form flat, even hulls for high performance racing yachts. In 1983, boats with S-2 Glass fiber in both hulls and decks captured all six class competitions and the overall title in the Southern Ocean Racing Conference in California.

In a related marine application, S-2 Glass fiber is giving increased strength, particularly in the bottom and over the ribs, to traditional canoe designs. In many cases, S-2 Glass fiber and aramid fibers are hybridized to contribute high specific strength as well as rigidity for high compression characteristics at low finished weights.

Military Applications

The Bell AH1S was the first military helicopter equipped with composite blades; and following in its footsteps, the Boeing CH47D, currently part of the CH47 modernization program, is also being equipped with S-2 fiber reinforced composite rotor blades. In most cases, the composite blades consist of filament wound S-2 Glass fiber spars with either S-2 Glass fiber or E glass trailing edge skins. The trailing edge core is made from nomex honeycomb material.

In aircraft fuel tanks, new safety standards are helping S-2 Glass fiber composites make major inroads for military applications. A survivable fuel tank is currently being used on CH-53 helicopters and F18 carrier based fighter aircraft. The tanks are filament wound of a hybrid of 80 percent S-2 Glass fiber and 20 percent graphite. The reason for selection is three-fold; puncture resistance, ability to withstand an 1,800°F fire for 15 minutes without fuel loss and durability to survive accidental jettisoning from the aircraft.

S-2 Glass fiber is helping the military protect U.S. borders. Boeing's AWACS 20-foot diameter radome, an early warning and control system, is constructed with S-2 Glass reinforcements. The pre-pregged S-2 Glass fabric is specified because of high strength, high temperature resistance, and radar transparency.

Since the mid-1970's, the dragon anti-tank weapons composite launch tube has been made with S-2 Glass braided yarn-reinforced resin. Today, the SMAW missile employs the material for high strength, light weight and low cost. S-2 Glass fiber is also used in the motor case and exhaust of the MX strategic missile; again cost and performance advantages over other materials are cited as reasons for the choice.

In ballistics applications, the Army currently is purchasing protective vests with S-2 Glass fiber for helicopter pilots. The vests were developed by the Natick R&D command in Natick, Massachusetts. S-2 Glass fiber was specified as a cost effective material choice to backup the vest's ceramic armor. These successes have led to the evaluation of S-2 Glass fiber for rigid armor. At the Army Materials and Mechanics Research Center in Watertown, Massachusetts, material evaluation focussed on track and wheel - structural armor systems. At the David Taylor Naval Ship R&D Laboratories in Bethesda, Maryland, researchers are looking at S-2 fiber for shipboard and vehicle armor.

A joint program between the Army Materials and Mechanics Research Center and Owens-Corning was conducted to determine the best combination of fiber finish (size) and fiber content to yield the optimum combination of ballistic and mechanical properties. OCF was contracted to fabricate a series of S-2 woven roving composite armor specimens for AMMRC to ballistically and mechanically evaluate. The results of this work using standard polyester is shown in Table IX. The only variable was the size sprayed on the glass during manufacturing. Sizings used were classified as to their compatibility with polyester resin as follows:

- a. Noncompatible
- b. Moderately compatible
- c. Compatible

TABLE IX
Effect of Fiber Finish on S-2 Glass® Structural Armor

OCF Product Code (psi)	Glass Size Compatibility with Polyester Resins	Relative Ballistic Performance	Flexural Strength
635	Non-Compatible (Starch/Oil)	100%	16,400
463	Moderately Compatible (Epoxy Compatible)	93%	24,900
P-365	Compatible (Polyester Compatible)	85%	48,400

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As observed in Table IX, the relative ballistic ranking shows that noncompatible size gives better ballistics protection. The compatible size yields the lowest relative ballistic ranking. Structural strength value shows inverse relationship with the compatible size having superior flexural strength. This small amount of data shows that the vehicle designer may tailor the composite properties depending on the specific component requirements. With this data and the continued cooperation of the Army, the future for light weight composites in the production of light and medium weight ground combat vehicles is certainly bright.

Additional work has been done in larger structures for wheeled vehicles. For example, the Marine Corps is currently conducting a demonstration program which involves the design and prototype fabrication of a reinforced plastics demonstration vehicle similar to the M113APC. AMMRC is also currently working with FMC to design and fabricate a turret structure for the Bradley fighting vehicle using S-2 Glass/polyester structural armor. The design phase has been completed and the fabrication phase has begun. The program had the goal of weight reduction while maintaining current ballistic and performance requirements. Work to-date has shown that a weight savings can be realized and that future turrets could be manufactured at a lower cost than current aluminum turrets.

Additional work is being done in military helmets to demonstrate the ballistic, structural, processing and cost performance advantages of S-2 Glass fiber. According to Ingalls, the use of composites on board naval ships can provide two major attributes for the builder. They are reduced weight and costs. In designing composites systems, the number of types and kinds of materials permit one to build in many survivable features such as armor, electromagnetic features, thermal, acoustical, and resin related improvement in flame retardancy, non-smoke and non-toxic properties. Ingalls Shipbuilding has also conducted extensive testing of S-2 Glass fiber versus other fibers, and the results have been very encouraging.

To expand the available database on S-2 Glass fiber-reinforced composites, Owens-Corning enlisted the University of Dayton to conduct substantial ballistic testing. The testing was completed in February, 1985. The results of this work is significant.

S-2 Glass fibers' exceptional strength to weight ratio makes it ideal for rigid armor because tensile strength is a key contributor to both ballistic and structural performance in glass fiber reinforced laminates. The fibers' high ultimate elongation (5.4 percent) also plays an important role in the impact absorbing ballistic mechanism. S-2 Glass fiber - reinforced laminates also allow a degree of design flexibility unavailable with other composite materials.

The University of Dayton Research Institute testing program confirms that in ballistic laminates of equal areal density, S-2 Glass appears to be superior to Kevlar-29 in ballistic performance for a threat typical to military vehicles and shipboard applications. Testing also confirms S-2 Glass ballistic laminates perform better than ballistic-grade E glass and 5083 aluminum as shown on Table X.

TABLE X

OCF is currently applying the new ballistic technology to thin, hybrid and spaced armor concepts. This will position S-2 Glass armor as the most cost/effective ballistic performer in new applications such as helmets, personnel armor, shelters and tactical military vehicles ...

Summary and Conclusions

S-2 Glass fiber offers excellent performance benefits such as high tensile, impact and fatigue strengths at a cost between E glass and other high performance fibers, such as aramid and carbon. Alone or hybridized with high-modulus materials, S-2 Glass fiber opens up many composite applications hitherto unachievable because of the performance limitations of E glass composites and metals and the high cost of other fibers. Currently available in roving, yarn, fabric, woven roving and chopped strands, S-2 Glass fiber is rapidly becoming the high performance, low cost reinforcement alternative for a myriad of applications in the composites revolution.